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SiC and Si detectors comparison for high carbon energy spectrometry

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ABSTRACT: An innovative SiC Schottky junction and a traditional p-n Si surface barrier detector have been compared to detect carbon ions with MeVs kinetic energy. To this, a comparison was performed during Rutherford backscattering spectrometry (RBS) using 2–10 MeV carbon ion beams. The energy resolution and detection efficiency for RBS analysis using the two detectors and their detection electronics are presented.

The detector parameters dependencies on the surface passivating layers, ion energy and current dependence, ion penetration depth, detection efficiency, energy resolution, and others are discussed.

The comparison of RBS analysis with SiC and Si is investigated highlighting the advantages and disadvantages of using SiC with respect to the traditional Si surface barrier detectors. The two detectors employed for proton, helium and carbon RBS spectrometry of different targets have been also compared on the base of the literature data.

KEYWORDS: Interaction of radiation with matter; Radiation-hard detectors; Solid state detectors

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1 Introduction

In previous experiments the SiC and Si comparison has been investigated using helium [1] and proton [2] beams applied to Rutherford backscattering spectrometry (RBS). The Si development in the last twenty years has permitted to optimize of its employment for RBS spectrometry for MeVs alpha and proton ion beams. In this paper, we want to highlight the differences in RBS spectra acquired using SiC-Schottky diode and Si p-n junction detectors of energetic carbon ions.

SiC is a prototype and is not optimized for these surface analyses, but we want to verify if it has sufficient energy resolution and sensitivity to permit qualitative and quantitative analysis of the investigated targets.

The used SiC detectors have a surface-active zone from 2 mm² up to 9 mm², a maximum depletion layer of 80 microns depth and a thin film surface metallization realized with Ni₂Si compound. They permit to detect of carbon ions from a minimum energy of about 400 keV up to a maximum value of about 400 MeV, as reported in the literature [3, 4].

The SiC energy resolution and sensitivity for helium and proton beams are comparable but slightly worse than Si barrier detectors. With this investigation, we want to know these parameters for 2–10 MeV carbon ions in RBS configuration from calibrated targets.

Has been demonstrated that Rutherford backscattering spectrometry (RBS) using 2–3 MeV helium and proton beams, normally obtained using Si detectors, can be performed also using SiC detectors with the advantage of having devices more resistant to high temperature, high radiation doses, intense visible radiation, and high fluence of heavy ion beams [5–7].

Generally, the surface barrier radiation detectors employed for high-resolution charge-particle spectrometry are represented by p-n junction partially depleted Si detectors and have a high sensitivity due to the low energy gap (1.1 eV) and energy requested to generate an *e-h* pair (3.6 eV). They have a minimum depletion depth of the order of 1000 μm and an active surface from 25 mm² to more than 100 mm², as well as those produced by Ortec [8]. Are polarized with a low reverse bias of the order of 50 V and their reverse current is of the order of 50 nA. Their surface is covered by about 10 nm Au and the Si dead layer thickness is of the order of 20 nm. Their energy resolution is high and, for 5 MeV alpha particles, is of the order of 0.05% [8].

The main characteristics of the SiC Schottky detector are represented by its active depletion layer of the order of 80 μm for a reverse bias of about 500 V with a reverse current of the order of 0.1 nA, by its energy gap of 3.3 eV, and by the surface nickel silicide with a thickness between 20–200 nm and a density of 7.4 g/cm³ [9].

SiC detectors are able to detect UV and X-rays, energetic electrons and ions, which can be used for different applications, from plasma monitoring spectrometry to ion time-of-flight measurements, from high-power diodes and transistors to different biomedical applications [10–13].

In this paper, we want to compare the RBS carbon ion spectrometry performed with SiC with that obtainable using classic Si barrier surface detectors.

To this we will use monoenergetic carbon beams with energy between 2 and 10 MeV incident on different solid targets placed in high vacuum, recording the Rutherford backscattered particles with SiC and Si both placed at 165° angle in high vacuum conditions.

To take into consideration the different ion energy loss in SiC, based on 4H-SiC semiconductor, and Si detector, and the different parameters characterizing the two devices, some data are reported in comparison in table 1.

Table 1. Some physical properties of SiC and Si detectors.

Material property	Silicon Carbide (4H-SiC)	Silicon	Detector property	SiC (Scottky)	Si (p-n)
Band gap (eV)	3.26	1.12	Depletion layer (μm)	80	1000
Mass density (g/cm^3)	3.21	2.33	Active surface area (mm^2)	9	25
Mean e-h pair energy (eV)	7.78	3.63	Surface metallization (nm)	Ni ₂ Si (200)	Au (10)
Electrons mobility ($\text{cm}^2/\text{V s}$)	900	1500	Reverse current (nA)	0.1	10
Holes mobility ($\text{cm}^2/\text{V s}$)	110	550	Carbon Stopping Power at 2 MeV ($\text{keV}/\mu\text{m}$)	1798	1177
Thermal conductivity ($\text{W}/\text{cm }^\circ\text{C}$)	4.0	1.5	Carbon Range at 2 MeV (μm)	1.62	2.45
Displacement energy (eV)	25	18	Carbon Energy loss in the dead layers at 2 MeV (keV)	518.4	74.6
Effective atomic number	12.54	14	Detection efficiency at 2 MeV	60%	100%
Maximum working temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)	600	300	Subtended solid angle (mstr)	2.13	3.16

2 Materials and methods

The carbon beams (2–10 MeV) have been obtained at the 3 MV Tandetron accelerator of the Nuclear Physics Institute (NPI) of the Academy of Science of the Czech Republic in Rez-Prague [14]. The carbon current was almost always kept at 10 nA but tests were also done with currents between 0.1 nA and 50 nA. The carbon spot was about 1 mm², thus normally the current density was 1 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$.

For this investigation, a calibration target was prepared and analyzed by 2.0 MeV helium RBS analysis. It consists of a Si substrate (300 μm thick) with three different covering thin films deposited

by physical vapor deposition (PVD) in high vacuum. Starting from the surface, the triple film is composed of 130 nm Au thin film, deposited on 98 nm Ag thin film, deposited on 55 nm Cu thin film, and deposited on the Si bulk substrate.

The Ortec detector (A series) was a partially depleted silicon surface barrier with 25 mm² surface area, polarized at 50 V, with 1000 μm active depth [6]. Its leakage reverse current was about 10–20 nA. The Si detector was placed at an 89 mm distance from the target and at a 165° backscattering angle, covering a solid angle of 3.16 mstr,

The SiC Schottky detector, realized as a prototype some years ago at ST-microelectronics, in collaboration with CNR-IMM of Catania, Italy [15], was used reversely polarized at 200 V bias, at which the leakage current was 0.1 nA, as measured with a Keithely instrumentation at room temperature and in high vacuum (10⁻⁶ mbar). It uses 4H-SiC epitaxial layers, 80 μm thick, with 10¹⁴ cm⁻³ dopant concentration onto an n-type heavily doped substrate. Ohmic contacts on the sample back side were formed by sputtering a 200 nm thick nickel film. The front contacts were obtained by sputtering deposition of a Ni thick film and performing a rapid thermal processing at 700°C producing the formation of Ni₂Si 200 nm thick. The active surface was 3 mm × 3 mm, characterized by the 200 nm Ni₂Si layers having a density of 7.4 g/cm³. The SiC detector was placed at a 65 mm distance from the target and at a 165° backscattering angle, covering a solid angle of 2.13 mstr.

The low detection solid angles used in the experiment and the low carbon ion current avoid any pile-up effect in the acquired RBS spectra.

Figure 1 shows a photo of the used SiC (a) and Si (b) detectors. Figure 1c reports a sectional view of the device employed in this experiment.

Figure 1. Photo of the SiC (a) and of the Si (b) detectors and a sectional view of the SiC device (c).

Figure 2 reports the detection efficiency of the used SiC detector calculated using the ion energy loss in its assembly structure relatives to protons, helium and carbon ion beams versus the ion energy.

Figure 2. Detection efficiency of SiC detector versus proton, helium and carbon ion energy.

The detection efficiency curves are agreed with the literature and indicate that carbon ions can be detected from about 400 keV, due to the energy loss in the surface metallization, up to about 400 MeV, due to the limited depletion layer of 80 microns.

Both detectors have been employed using a preamplifier (Ortec mod. 142 A), followed by a linear amplifier (Ortec mod. 672) with 0.1 μ s shaping time and a very compact digital Multi-Channel Analyzer (MCA, Amptek MCA-8000D) to digitize the analogical input signal and to acquire the RBS spectra on PC.

RBS analyses performed using 2–10 MeV carbon beams were performed by considering the kinematic backscattering factor depending on the target element, the backscattering detection angle, the energy of the backscattered particle with respect to that of the incident one, and by considering the differential scattering Rutherford cross sections in the laboratory system [16, 17].

The SIMNRA code was employed to simulate the RBS spectra analysis and to evaluate qualitatively and quantitatively the amount of the elements detected in the analyzed target [18].

The energy-stopping powers, penetration depth, electronic and nuclear energy loss and energy straggling in the different materials have been calculated using the SRIM code of Ziegler [19].

3 Results and discussion

The triple film of calibration realized at NPI for this investigation, was analyzed in composition and in thickness by 2.0 MeV helium RBS spectrometry and by proton-induced X-ray fluorescence (PIXE) analysis. The calibration target corresponds to the reported thickness measurements of Au (130 nm)/Ag (98 nm)/Cu (55 nm) thin pure films deposited on the silicon substrate.

A first investigation on the SiC and Si comparison has been performed by the RBS analysis of the carbon ions backscattered (165°) by a multi-element target, the Au (130 nm)/Ag (98 nm)/Cu (55 nm) thin films deposited on a silicon substrate.

Figure 3 reports the SiC (a) and Si (b) comparison obtained using 2.0 MeV, 10 nA, 1000 s detection time, and incident carbon ions.

Figure 3. RBS spectra at 2.0 MeV C⁺ comparison for SiC (a) and Si (b) of C ions backscattered by the Au/Ag/Cu/Si target.

The kinematic factors of the carbon ions at 165° for the target elements are 0.7866, 0.6443, 0.4712 and 0.1655 for Au, Ag, Cu and Si, respectively [17]. Thus, the backscattered carbon ions from such elements will have a maximum kinetic energy of 1.57 MeV, 1.29 MeV, 0.94 MeV and 0.33 MeV, respectively. The corresponding channel-energy calibration factor is 7.0 keV/ch and 2.9 keV/ch for the SiC and the Si recorded spectrum, respectively. Spectra show a clear higher energy resolution for carbon ion detection by Si with respect to SiC one. The different ion yields (counts) are due to the different solid angles subtended by the two detectors and to the different energy requests to produce $e-h$ pairs in the two semiconductors.

The low-energy carbon ions backscattered by the target silicon surface, corresponding to a maximum value of about 330 keV, cannot be detected because they are stopped in the surface metallization film of the SiC detector, while they are detected by the Si one having less dense and less thick surface dead layers.

The Rutherford backscattering cross section increases with the square of the atomic number of the target elements, thus is expected a yield reduction (counts) with the atomic number of the element [16]. Such reduction is more evident due to the decreasing thickness of the element films from Au to Ag and Cu. The RBS spectrum acquired by Si is as expected, while the SiC one is not because the low energetic C ions backscattered from the Cu thin film are detected very near to the metal electrode of the SiC Schottky junction and are collected better than the C ions having higher penetration depth and produced far from the collection electrode. This effect is not observed in the case of Si detector due to the higher electron and hole mobilities with respect to those of SiC (see table 1).

Figure 4 reports the SiC (a) and Si (b) spectra comparison obtained using 3.0 MeV, 10 nA, 1000 s detection time, and incident carbon ions in the same previously described target. In this case, the backscattered carbon ions from the cited elements will have a maximum kinetic energy of 2.36 MeV, 1.93 MeV, 1.41 MeV and 0.50 MeV, respectively. The corresponding channel-energy calibration factor is 7.0 keV/ch and 3.1 keV/ch for the SiC and the Si recorded spectrum, respectively.

In this case, the SiC detects the carbon ions backscattered from the silicon substrate because their energy has become higher than that absorbed in the surface metallization film. Moreover, the Si/Au

Figure 4. RBS spectra at 3.0 MeV C^+ comparison for SiC (a) and Si (b) of C ions backscattered by the Au/Ag/Cu/Si target.

yield ratio and the Cu/Au yield ratio are higher for SiC with respect to the Si detector, indicating that the collection of the $e-h$ pair is good because occurs very near to the surface metallic electrode.

Now we enhance the C ion energy to 5.0 MeV energy and observe the modified RBS spectra. Figure 5 reports the SiC (a) and Si (b) spectra comparison obtained using 5.0 MeV, 10 nA, 1000 s acquisition time, and incident carbon ions in the same previously described calibration target.

Figure 5. RBS spectra at 5.0 MeV C^+ comparison for SiC (a) and Si (b) of C ions backscattered by the Au/Ag/Cu/Si target.

The backscattered carbon ions from the cited elements will have a maximum kinetic energy of 3.93 MeV, 3.22 MeV, 2.36 MeV and 0.83 MeV, respectively. The corresponding channel-energy calibration factor is 6.95 keV/ch and 3.2 keV/ch for the SiC and the Si recorded spectrum, respectively.

Again, the detected carbon yield for Si is higher than SiC due to the higher detection solid angle, higher detection efficiency, higher $e-h$ mobility and minor energy to produce the $e-h$ pairs.

The best energy resolution is evident by the very distinct peaks due to Si and Cu in the case of the Si detector and, instead, near over-imposed peaks in the case of the SiC detector. In this case, the carbon ions, also at low energy, have a major penetration depth, i.e. are produced far from the surface electrode of SiC, thus the Si/Au and Cu/Au yield ratios are similar between SiC and Si detectors.

Moreover, the significant carbon ion penetration in the silicon substrate of the target indicates a not Gaussian peak of silicon, but a cassette spectrum due to its considerable thickness, as expected.

Finally, a last measure was performed using 10 MeV carbon ions at the same current of 10 nA and 1000 s acquisition time on the same previously described target of reference.

Figure 6 reports the SiC (a) and Si (b) comparison obtained using 10.0 MeV, 10 nA, 100 s acquisition time, and incident carbon ions in the same previous reference target.

Figure 6. RBS spectra at 10.0 MeV C^+ comparison for SiC (a) and Si (b) of C ions backscattered by the Au/Ag/Cu/Si target.

In this case the backscattered carbon ions from the cited elements will have a maximum kinetic energy of 7.87 MeV, 6.44 MeV, 4.71 MeV and 1.66 MeV, respectively. The corresponding channel-energy calibration factor is 7.47 keV/ch and 3.50 keV/ch for the SiC and the Si recorded spectrum, respectively.

Again, the detected carbon yield for Si is higher than SiC due to the higher detection solid angle, higher detection efficiency, higher $e-h$ mobility and minor energy to produce the $e-h$ pairs.

The backscattered carbon ions having higher penetration depth in the SiC and Si are produced far from the surface electrode of SiC, thus the Si/Au and Cu/Au yield ratio are similar between SiC and Si detectors and the pair collection does not depend on edge effects. In this case, in fact, the significant carbon ion penetration in the silicon target substrate, of about 9.47 microns, indicates a not Gaussian peak of the thick silicon, as expected for its considerable thickness, and the 7.87 MeV carbons, scattered by Au, penetrate up to about 4.86 microns in SiC. The better energy resolution of Si compared to SiC is very evident from the sharp edge of the silicon signal compared to the very smooth edge of the signal acquired with the SiC detector.

The energy resolution comparison for Si and SiC can be performed by the full width at half maximum (FWHM) for the free RBS peaks due to Au, Ag and Cu. Table 2 shows the evaluated energy resolutions measured for the two detectors from the RBS peaks of the spectra reported in figure 6, relative to the backscattered 10 MeV carbon ions. At high-energy carbon ions, the SiC energy resolution appears nearly comparable to that of a silicon detector.

Although the increase in energy of the carbon ions leads to a better energy resolution of the element peaks seen by the RBS via the SiC detector, the spectra of the Si detector always remain better highlighted and resolved.

Table 2. Comparison of the Si and SiC energy resolutions from RBS spectra for 10 MeV carbon ion backscattering.

Element by RBS peak	C-Energy (MeV)	Silicon detector		SiC detector	
		FWHM (keV)	Resolution (%)	FWHM (keV)	Resolution (%)
Au	7.87	228	2.90	329	4.18
Ag	6.44	217	3.37	276	4.28
Cu	4.71	228	4.84	232	4.92

A detailed analysis of the different energy resolution with the two detectors can be extracted by RBS spectra comparing, for example, the carbon atoms backscattered from the Ag thin film. To this, the spectra were compared at 2 MeV and 10 MeV incident carbon ions.

The first comparison (figure 7a) was obtained normalizing to the same calibration energy and backscattered yield of the Si detector when 2.0 MeV carbon ions are employed. In this case, the different peak width between SiC and Si corresponds to 9 keV and the SiC energy resolution is worse than Si in quantity $9 \text{ keV}/1290 \text{ keV} = 0.7\%$.

The second comparison (figure 7b) was obtained normalizing to the same calibration energy and backscattered yield of the Si detector when 10.0 MeV carbon ions are employed. In this case, the different peak width between SiC and Si corresponds to 29 keV and the SiC energy resolution is worse than Si in quantity $29 \text{ keV}/6440 \text{ keV} = 0.045\%$.

Figure 7. SiC and Si comparison of the RBS carbon peak of Ag at 2.0 MeV and 10.0 MeV Carbon ions.

Thus, the SiC detector appears less energetic resolution with respect to Si one but presents increasingly similar energy resolution for the detection of high-energy ions.

Based on the results presented we can consider the Ortec Si detector certainly better than they used SiC detector, however, the latter may present some advantages compared to the Si detector which cannot be overlooked in the following cases:

- 1) Ion irradiation of luminescent and photoluminescent targets emitting in the visible region under ion bombardment, resulting in a significant disturb of the Si detector and RBS spectra acquired using silicon show a high considerable background which makes it impossible to use unless

behind a light absorber. This effect cannot be seen by SiC detectors, even to thinner surface metallizations or interdigitated metallizations, due to their greater energy gap, which produces background only for UV and X-ray detection but not for visible radiation, in agreement with the literature [20–22].

- 2) Si detector cannot operate at high temperature due to its high leakage current which becomes high for temperatures of the order of 100°C generating a high noise and irreversibly worsening the energy resolution of the detector. Execution of RBS analyses in high-temperature conditions is not possible for the Si spectra deterioration, while they remain possible using SiC, which shows a leakage current about two order of magnitude lower than Si and a minor dependence on the temperature, according to the literature [2, 7, 23].
- 3) Using high absorbed doses and ion fluence, long irradiation times and heavy ion detection, it is evident the less damage to SiC detectors with respect to the Si one. Silicon detector loses its better energy resolution in these cases while SiC maintains a good energy resolution. This effect is due to the higher atomic binding energy of the SiC structure with respect to the Si one. The average life of SiC detectors is greater than those based on Si and at high currents and doses and detecting heavy ions does not significantly worsen its energy resolution, according to recent literature data [20, 24].

Further investigations have been performed using other ion beams, such as protons, helium and nitrogen beams at 2.0 MeV energy, analyzing in RBS the same target surface. Measurements have demonstrated that the energy resolution of SiC worsens to about 1.8% using 2 MeV protons and to 1.2% using 2 MeV helium and improves to 0.5% using 2 MeV nitrogen. Further considerations on these investigations are reported in previous papers [1, 2].

Thus, heavy ion detection improves the energy resolution of SiC making it like that of a silicon detector.

However, it is important to highlight that the SiC detector represents only a prototype that should be further optimized to be able to be used for RBS spectroscopic analyses. The surface Ni₂Si electrode thickness should be reduced, or modified using an interdigit metallization, the active region in areas and depth should be enhanced, guard rings should be used to improve the *e-h* pair collection, and detection electronics improved in aspects especially signal preamplification.

The research activity concerning the use of SiC and Si detectors versus the type of ion beam, target composition and temperature is in progress and will be better reported in the next paper.

4 Conclusions

The SiC-Schottky detectors are very used for many applications, such as for laser-generated plasma to monitor the emitted UV, X-rays, energetic ions and electrons. They are used for measurements of time-of-flight of accelerated ions, for gas puff of UV and X-ray emission employed for innovative microscopy, for tokamak applications to measure the characteristic energy of the particles emitted from nuclear fusion processes, for high power p-n junction operating at high voltage and having higher efficiency, fast switching speeds, and high thermal conductivity and for high-frequency and high-temperature microelectronic device applications.

This paper has investigated the possibility of using SiC for RBS surface spectrometry using 2–10 MeV carbon beams, similar to previous contributions obtained using protons and helium beams.

We have demonstrated that SiC diodes detect carbon ions with energy in the range of about 500 keV up to about 300 MeV with a good energy resolution to be used for RBS carbon spectrometry, like silicon detectors employable for qualitative and quantitative RBS analyses. The used SiC prototype has a surface-active area of 3 mm × 3 mm, with 200 nm thickness in Ni₂Si alloy, and 80 microns active region depth.

RBS measurements demonstrated that the SiC energy resolution is comparable to that of Si, although a little worse. On the other side, Ortec Si-barrier detectors have high energy resolution and are optimized for ion spectrometry such as RBS by helium beams. They have a very thin Au surface metallization and dead layers to reduce the ion energy loss of the incident ions and the Ortec preamplifier and amplifier are optimized to enhance their signal-to-noise ratio and acquire RBS spectra with a minimum background.

SiC Schottky detectors, instead, do not have high energy resolution such as Si one, but offer some important advantages. It consists of the higher energy gap, that permits it to be transparent to visible radiation and to be used also in the presence of high intensity visible light, has a lower reverse current, of about two order of magnitude lower with respect to Si, is radiation resistant due to the higher bonding energy Si-C with respect to Si-Si, making it possible to use even in harsh conditions, such as plasmas, high temperatures and high absorbed doses.

The SiC optimization may permit to realize of ion detectors very competitive with those based on silicon and very useful to detect heavy and high energy ions.

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